

BLUEMISSIONAA

Building a coordination hub to support the mission
implementation in the *Atlantic and Arctic Basin*

BLUEMISSIONAA AT MACARONIGHT 2024 IN GRAN CANARIA

EUROPEAN RESEARCHER'S NIGHT

This project has received funding from the European Union's
Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under
Grant Agreement number 101093962.

Document Information

Project Name	BlueMissionAA – Building a coordination hub to support the Mission implementation in the Atlantic and Arctic Basin
Grant Number	101093962
Deliverable number	
Deliverable title	BLUEMISSIONAA AT MACARONIGHT 2024 IN GRAN CANARIA - Report
WP number	WP5
Deliverable due date	
Submission date	
Dissemination levels	
Lead beneficiary	
Author(s)	Ivan Sá Vieira, Diana Sousa
Contributors	
Internal reviewers	Diana Sousa

Document history and changes

Version	Date	Author	Description
0.1	17/10/2024	Ivan Sá Vieira	1 st Draft
0.2	24/10/2024	Diana Sousa	Minor Revision
0.3			
1			

Authors | NA

Publisher | NA

How to cite | NA

Supported by/In partnership with

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1. Introduction

Macaronight is part of the *European Researchers' Night* project financed by Marie Curie Sklodowska actions, and involves partners from Madeira, the Azores, Gran Canaria and Tenerife. It aims to bring researchers from Macaronesia closer to the citizens, especially the younger ones, so that they can know more about their research, the benefits that it brings to society and the impact that it has on everyday life.

The sixth edition of *European Researchers' Night*, the Macaronight 2024, focused on the theme "Missions of Horizon Europe", highlighting the research related to three mission within Horizon Europe program – "Adaptation to Climate Change", "Restore our Oceans and Waters", and "A Soil Deal for Europe". The event took place on September 26th and 27th, across eight venues, attracting over 10,200 visitors, with more than 320 researchers showcasing their work to the public.

BlueMissionAA, as part of the European Mission to "Restore our Ocean and Waters," played a key role at the Museum Elder of Science and Technology, the venue in Gran Canaria. Its activities were designed to teach ocean literacy and raise awareness about marine restoration through interactive and playful learning experiences. The session designed by Sociedade Portuguesa de Inovação (SPI) with the support from the Oceanic Platform of the Canary Islands (PLOCAN), featured hands-on, gamified activities that allowed children to explore ocean conservation in an engaging and educational way.

Over the two-day event, more than 500 children (aged 6-12) participated in these activities, learning about the importance of protecting our oceans. Alongside them, a number of researchers and collaborators showcased their efforts in marine science, contributing to the event's success in inspiring the next generation of ocean advocates.

2. Key Activities

The BlueMissionAA campaign at Macaronight 2024 featured a series of engaging, hands-on activities designed to educate children about ocean conservation and restoration. These activities aimed to spark curiosity, encourage critical thinking, and foster creativity, all while reinforcing the core principles of ocean literacy. From interactive murals and games to creative expression through drawing and painting, each activity was carefully crafted to make learning about the ocean both fun and meaningful. Here, we highlight the key activities that captivated the young participants and helped them connect with the mission to protect and restore our oceans.

2.1 BlueMission AA Stand and Branding

Figure 1 - BlueMissionAA represented by SPI (Diana Sousa and Ivan Sá Vieira)

Figure 2 - BlueMissionAA stand at Macaronight 2024

A special set of BlueMissionAA T-shirts was developed for the Macaronight 2024 edition as well to be worn by the educators. The T-shirts featured a simple design with the BlueMissionAA logo on the front and Macaronight 2024 logo on the back.

Figure 3 - BlueMissionAA T-shirt (front)

Figure 4 - BlueMissionAA T-shirt (back)

2.1 BlueMissionAA Ocean Literacy Booklet

The BlueMissionAA Ocean Literacy booklet, developed in Spanish, is an educational resource designed to promote awareness about ocean conservation literacy, and restoration, particularly for younger audiences (from 6-12). The booklet highlights BlueMissionAA's goals aligned with the European Union's Mission to "Restore Our Ocean and Waters by 2030". Through the use of colorful visuals, engaging and age-adapted language, as well as an interactive drawing activity, the booklet introduces key concepts related to ocean ecosystems, the threats they face, and most importantly how individuals can contribute to their preservation, daily. This final component is at the core of the Citizen Engagement activities under BlueMissionAA, to advocate for action and participatory learning methods of the best practices.

The Booklet covers a wide range of topics including the importance of oceans for climate regulation, biodiversity, food security, and the global economy. Instances of best practices emphasized are: the significance of sustainable seafood choices, pollution reduction, and marine-protected areas.

COVER

PAGE 5

PAGE 10

PAGE 11

Figure 5 - BlueMissionAA Ocean Literacy Booklet - Spanish Version

For instances, page 5 offers practical and simple actions children can take to protect the ocean, such as volunteering for coral reef restoration or participating in coastal clean-ups. The goal is to empower them with the knowledge of how their everyday actions can help maintain healthy oceans, emphasizing personal responsibility.

For example, page 10 encourages children to further explore ocean ecosystems through books, documentaries, online resources, and even citizen science initiatives. It adds value by showing that learning about the ocean is an ongoing journey, sparking curiosity and a deeper commitment to marine conservation.

Finally, on the last page an interactive activity allows children to illustrate their own marine ecosystem, reinforcing their understanding of marine life, habitats, and food chains. It merges education with creativity, making learning about ocean conservation both enjoyable and personal. Often the results from these can be quite telling of the perspective of children after the engagement activity, as displayed in the murals (later in the report).

2.1 BlueMission AA Posters

As an additional strategy to supplement BlueMissionAA's efforts to enhance ocean literacy among children, a poster featuring QR codes linking to ocean-themed documentaries was developed. This poster, offered children through their teachers and parents a convenient way to engage with additional ocean literacy resources.

By scanning the QR codes, viewers can access a variety of documentaries, such as Blue Planet, which delve into marine ecosystems, the importance of ocean conservation, and the global efforts to restore ocean health. These visual resources, though in no way developed by the European Commission or the project, can be leveraged to enhance learning experiences, complement the booklet's interactive activities and knowledge-building sections by offering dynamic, real-world examples of marine environments and restoration initiatives.

As part of the educational pitch developed by the team, teachers were encouraged to integrate these documentaries into classroom discussions or lessons about marine science and conservation. Moreover, teachers were asked to pass the recommendations to the children's parents to further foster a home environment that supports ocean literacy.

Figure 6 - BlueMissionAA Ocean Literacy Documentaries Recommendations

A questionnaire was developed to assess the level of ocean literacy among children who participated in the activities. This served as a valuable tool to assess in broad terms what was the general knowledge over ocean literacy of the children after the activity. Note that no prior control was made, challenging the possibility to make direct linkages and comparisons and determine the impact of the interactive activities.

Teachers and/or parents (through the teachers) were encouraged by the BlueMissionAA representatives to complete the survey with the children to gather insights on their understanding of ocean preservation and restoration efforts.

The questions focused on practical and behavioral aspects of ocean literacy, aiming to gauge the children's awareness of ocean-related issues and their willingness to engage in conservation activities. Some examples of questions included: "¿Cuáles de estas actividades has hecho para ayudar a restaurar el océano? (Elige todas las que apliquen)" (*Which of these activities have you done to help restore the ocean? (Select all that apply)*)

This question aimed to identify which restoration activities the children had already participated in, offering insights into their previous exposure to marine conservation efforts.

"¿Qué actividad de restauración del océano te gustaría probar? (Elige hasta 3)" (*What ocean restoration activity would you like to try? (Choose up to 3)*)

This was designed to determine which new activities piqued the children's interest, guiding future efforts to design engaging restoration opportunities.

"¿Qué podrías hacer hoy para que el océano sea más saludable? (Elige una)" (*What could you do today to make the ocean healthier? (Choose one)*)

This question encouraged children to think about actionable steps they could take immediately to contribute to ocean health, promoting a sense of personal responsibility.

"¿Qué pequeño cambio podrías comenzar a hacer hoy para ayudar a proteger el océano? (Elige una)" (*What small change could you start making today to help protect the ocean? (Choose one)*)

Similar to the previous question, this focused on small, achievable changes in daily habits that could support ocean protection, reinforcing the idea that every individual can make a difference.

Additionally, demographic data such as age, sex, and school year was requested to help categorize responses and understand how different age groups and demographics responded to the material. Finally, by involving both teachers and parents, the questionnaire also served to extend the learning experience beyond the event, encouraging continued

discussion and awareness at home or in the classroom. Unfortunately, only one answer was registered.

For future iterations, a dedicated person for questionnaires could aid this data gathering, during the activity. Additionally, having prior and/or subsequent contact with the participant schools could help with effective dissemination. A further potential risk could be the dimension and type of questions selected for the questionnaire.

Figure 7 - BlueMissionAA Activity Survey

A poster was developed for the children attending the event to leave a meaningful message in post-its after taking a booklet, reinforcing the idea that our actions should always aim for balance, like a net-zero approach. The central message of the poster was to inspire the young participants to think about how every action we take has an impact, and that we should aim to maintain harmony with the environment. Just as we take resources from the ocean, we must give something back by ensuring the ocean has the time, conditions, and protection it needs to recover, flourish, and continue to support life.

Children were encouraged to reflect on this concept by leaving a message or drawing on the poster, symbolizing a commitment to making choices that keep nature in balance. This could be as simple as promising to reduce plastic use, volunteering for a beach clean-up, or learning more about sustainable seafood. Though, purposely, nothing or no example was

given right after the request to enable total expression of the children in regards to the concept. The interactive nature of this activity aimed firstly to instill a mindset of responsibility toward the ocean, encouraging children to consider the long-term impact of their actions, and secondly to tacitly assess their perspective over the discussed theme and efficacy of the activity. By encouraging participants to leave something behind—a message, a pledge, or a promise—they were symbolically practicing the idea of giving back after taking something, much like how we should treat the ocean and its ecosystems.

Figure 8 - BlueMissionAA Booklet Exchange Poster

MESSAGES LEFT

Figure 9 - Messages left by the participants

Note: Unfortunately, due to unforeseen issues with delivery, the 300 printed booklets did not arrive at the event and were returned to the sender by customs. As a mitigation strategy, the booklet was made available online, and teachers were encouraged to download and share it with their students and parents.

Descarga el cuadernillo en digital aquí

BLUEMISSION AA
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implementation in the Atlantic and Arctic Basin

Figure 10 - BlueMissionAA Booklet Digital Version Poster

2.2 BlueMissionAA Mural

Two large A0 murals were developed to provide a hands-on, interactive experience for children at the Museum Elder of Science and Technology. These murals served as both an educational tool and a creative outlet, allowing the children to express themselves through drawing, painting, and writing. Pre-drawn figures of corals, seaweed, fish, and divers encouraged them to engage with the concepts introduced during the initial talk about BlueMissionAA, ocean literacy, EU Mission Ocean, and marine restoration initiatives.

After the introduction, children were invited to leave their marks on the murals, resulting in a variety of creative and expressive outcomes. Some children painted with great precision, while others embraced a rather more spontaneous approach. For instance, one child painted a section entirely black, representing the pitch darkness of the ocean's deep, low-light regions. Others experimented with different shades of blue to mimic the sunlight being filtered through clouds, demonstrating their understanding of how light interacts with the ocean.

In addition to these visual representations, many children wrote messages on the mural. Some left pledges to take better care of the ocean, while others made pleas for people to stop littering the ocean. The mural also featured creative drawings of jellyfish, starfish, and fish, with a meticulous targetting of endangered species like sea turtles, calling out for their protection. Rather humorously, it was suggested that people should eat less sushi to help protect marine life. The murals also became a space for unexpected creativity, as children added submarines, cartoon characters, mentions of football players, and even chaotic scribbles. While some areas of the mural might have appeared as visual entropy, it was clear that every child was finding a unique way to interact with the concept of ocean conservation.

Overall, this activity was a huge success, drawing significant attention to the BlueMissionAA stand and earning praise from the young participants. The murals allowed the children to connect with ocean restoration in a personal and playful way, reinforcing the lessons of ocean literacy through creative expression. This hands-on activity highlighted the importance of making environmental education fun and interactive, helping to spark the children's imaginations and deepen their understanding of the vital role they play in protecting our oceans.

Figure 12 - BlueMissionAA Mural 1

Figure 11 - BlueMissionAA Mural 2

Figure 13 - BlueMissionAA Mural Progress 1

Figure 14 - BlueMissionAA Mural Progress 2

MURAL DETAILS

Figure 15 - BlueMissionAA Mural Details

2.3 BlueMissionAA - Macaronight 2024 "Angelote" Stamp

As an extra perk and branding detail, *BlueMissionAA* developed a special stamp for the children, designed to confirm and commemorate their visit to the stand, much like stamping a passport. This Macaronight special edition stamp featured the outline of an *angel shark*, or *angelote* (*squatina squatina*), an endangered species. Although the global population of angel sharks has decreased by about 80%, the Canary Islands remain a crucial stronghold for this species, where it can be found in healthy numbers and often seen in diving and fishing expeditions. Notably, Las Teresitas beach in Tenerife has become an important safe haven for the species.

BlueMissionAA chose to highlight this stronghold as a tribute to marine biodiversity resilience, the Canary Islands' essential contribution to the richness of the Atlantic Ocean, and the cultural importance of the region in protecting endangered species like the angel shark. The

stamp also celebrated positive conservation efforts, such as those of the *Angel Shark Conservation Network*, which serves as a beacon of successful environmental stewardship.

Much to the delight of *BlueMissionAA*, many children immediately recognized the outline of the angel shark and excitedly identified it as the "angelote," showcasing the excellent environmental education efforts of teachers, government, and local associations in the Canary Islands. The stamp became so popular that children began stretching their arms and requesting "tattoos" of the angel shark, a request that was happily fulfilled after the teachers' consent. This enthusiastic reception underscored both the effectiveness of the conservation efforts and the strong connection between the local community and their marine environment, and provided yet again a simple detail which certainly will be remembered by the participant children.

Figure 16 - BlueMissionAA - Macaronight 2024 "Angelote" Stamp

2.4 BlueMissionAA Macaronight Puzzle

BlueMissionAA developed a series of puzzles showcasing images of seabed restoration initiatives through artificial reefs. These puzzles featured both accidental reefs, such as scrap airplanes or shipwrecks, and purpose-built artificial reefs, designed to restore marine habitats. The activity aimed to engage children's minds by illustrating the ocean's incredible ability to incorporate foreign objects into its ecosystem and demonstrating the resilience of marine environments.

The purpose was by completing the puzzles, children would be encouraged to reflect on how, even when human-made structures end up on the seabed, marine life can adapt and thrive around these foreign bodies. However, the activity was also thought to serve as a reminder that accidental artificial reefs should not be promoted or seen as a solution to marine damage. Instead, it emphasized that with the right practices, we can responsibly enhance the ocean's natural ability to restore itself, through carefully planned initiatives that support the recovery and growth of marine ecosystems.

Note: Unfortunately, the puzzles did not arrive at the venue due to the same customs issue that affected the delivery of other materials. Despite our numerous attempts to resolve the issue, it was not possible to release the puzzles on time for the event.

Figure 17 - BlueMissionAA Macaronight Puzzle 2

Figure 18 - BlueMissionAA Macaronight Puzzle 1

2.5 BlueMissionAA Card Game

The *BlueMissionAA* card game was designed as a fun and educational tool to teach children about ocean conservation and restoration. It introduces the concepts of good and bad practices in a simple, interactive way, engaging young participants in thinking critically about how human actions impact the marine environment. The game consists of 36 cards, divided into four categories:

Green Cards, which represent the good practices and showcase actions that contribute positively to ocean health and restoration, such as: *Replanting Seagrass*: Helps stabilise sediments and restore ecosystems by providing habitat for marine life. *Coral Reef Restoration*: Involves transplanting nursery-grown corals to damaged reefs to promote recovery.

Red Cards highlight bad practices thus demonstrating harmful activities that threaten the ocean, like: *Overfishing*: Disrupts the balance of marine ecosystems and leads to species depletion. *Plastic Pollution*: Introduces harmful waste into the ocean, endangering marine life and ecosystems.

Blue Cards, "Did you know" fact cards provide interesting insights into marine life and ecosystems, designed to educate players while keeping the game fun. Examples include: "Did you know seagrass beds capture carbon 35 times faster than terrestrial forests?" These facts can prompt players to think about the importance of ocean ecosystems in combating climate change.

Yellow Cards, the question cards, which drive the gameplay, ask players to respond to questions related to ocean conservation, such as: "What small action could you take today to help protect marine life?"

The game can be played in several formats depending on the number of players and their ages. Typically, the red and green cards (bad and good practices) are laid out side by side on the table, and players are split into teams representing either the "good" or "bad" side. The deck of yellow question cards and blue fact cards are kept separate.

The game can be played in different ways. Usually, a player draws a yellow question card, reads the question aloud, and both teams attempt to answer by selecting a matching green or red card from their side. For example, if the question is "What could you do to improve water quality?" the team with the green cards might choose "Planting Oyster Larvae," since oysters help filter water and improve its quality. In another version of the game, a red card (bad practice) is drawn, and the opposing team must counter it by selecting a green card (good practice) that would help fix or mitigate the problem. For instance, if a player draws "Plastic Pollution," the team with the green cards could counter it with "Seafloor Cleanup," showing how to address the issue by removing harmful waste. Some questions purposely require more than one answer, allowing all players to participate by drawing multiple green and red cards. This variation shows that environmental issues often have widespread impacts that can't be solved by just one action. For example, overfishing might also lead to habitat destruction, and fixing this might involve multiple solutions such as establishing Marine Protected Areas and enforcing sustainable fishing practices. Finally, the blue fact cards can be used as a bonus round or to extend the game further. These cards are read aloud, and players have the opportunity to discuss the facts or match them with corresponding practices

from the red and green decks. This round is highly appreciated by children, who enjoy reading or listening to interesting facts, like how coral reefs support 25% of marine life despite covering less than 1% of the ocean floor. For younger children (6-8), who might find reading challenging, the game can be adapted by asking them to decide if the content of each card represents a good or bad practice without revealing the color coding. This playful approach helps reinforce the message while keeping the activity accessible to younger participants. Usually a bit of theatrical play can enhance the effectiveness of this format.

In sum, the card game is dynamic and gamifies education of children on a tough and complex topic such as ocean conservation. Most importantly, it encourages critical thinking about how our actions, both good and bad, affect marine ecosystems, also helps instill a sense of responsibility toward the ocean from a young age and finally it inserts the spirit of inter-team competition and intra-team cooperation to immerse the young participants.

Figure 19 - BlueMissionAA Macaronight Good and Bad Practices Card Game

PLAYING THE CARD GAME

Figure 20 - Children playing the BlueMissionAA Macaronight Good and Bad Practices Card Game 2

3. Conclusions

The 4th BlueMissionAA Citizen Campaign (milestone 17), held during Macaronight 2024 in Gran Canaria, successfully achieved several key outcomes, particularly in raising awareness of the EU Mission to "Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030". While the event had notable successes, there were also important lessons learned, especially in areas like data gathering and managing large groups of children. The campaign continued to advocate strongly for the preservation and restoration of the Atlantic and Arctic Basins.

The event attracted over 500 young participants, ranging in age from 6 to 12, from various schools in Gran Canaria. Overall, the children were highly receptive to the activities and engaged enthusiastically with the hands-on, creative tasks. Activities such as mural painting and drawing allowed the children to express themselves freely while reinforcing concepts related to ocean restoration. These creativity-enhancing activities proved to be an excellent way to connect with this age group, serving as a template for future events aimed at younger audiences. Moreover, gamification of learning through activities like the card game was one of the most effective aspects of the campaign. Dividing good and bad practices and engaging the children in critical thinking about ocean conservation worked exceptionally well, keeping them focused and excited. Unfortunately, the absence of the puzzle, which was meant to complement this learning experience, was a missed opportunity that would have enhanced the overall impact.

One area that proved to be more difficult was the survey aspect of the campaign. The surveys used to assess ocean literacy were likely too lengthy and not entirely age-appropriate for this younger audience. The feedback collected indicates that future iterations of the campaign should involve a more streamlined and child-friendly method of data collection. A more effective and engaging system for gathering data will be a key focus going forward.

Due to unexpected issues with the delivery of materials, the branding aspect of the event was not fully realized. While the original plan was to distribute 300 printed booklets, these did not arrive in time, and only the digital version was available. However, other branding elements, such as the special edition T-shirts, stamps, and visual displays, helped maintain the project's visibility and left a lasting impression on the participants.

Another challenge faced during the event was managing the varying sizes of student groups, which ranged from as few as 6 to as many as 40 children at a time. Larger groups made it difficult to ensure that each child had equal opportunities to engage with the activities. The reduced number of activities (due to the absence of the puzzle and physical booklets) also contributed to some logistical difficulties in maintaining the children's attention, in the larger

groups. It was made clear that smaller groups are more effective, or extra activities and extra personell to break down bigger groups into smaller ones.

In addition, a key factor in the success of the event was the invaluable support from the teachers who accompanied the students. Their assistance in managing the children and overcoming language barriers was crucial to keeping the participants engaged and helping them understand the core messages of the event. The collaboration with the teachers greatly contributed to the smooth running of the sessions and highlighted the importance of involving educators more deeply in future campaigns.

4. Annex

Survey Macaronight 2024

Los campos marcados con * son obligatorios.

Building a coordination hub to support the Mission implementation in the Atlantic and Arctic Basin

Consentimiento

Por la presente, doy mi consentimiento para el uso de mis datos personales de acuerdo con el Reglamento General de Protección de Datos (RGPD) de la Unión Europea, con el fin de cumplir los propósitos de BlueMissionAA en el evento Macaronight 2024. Entiendo que el uso de mis datos estará limitado exclusivamente a esta actividad y se restringirá a lo absolutamente necesario, con el objetivo de obtener información demográfica. Asimismo, se tomarán las medidas adecuadas para garantizar la protección de mi privacidad y confidencialidad en todo momento.

Acepto las condiciones propuestas

Datos demográficos

* Edad

* Sexo

- Masculino
 Femenino
 Prefiero no contestar

* Grado

Consulta

¡Hola, Ayudantes del Océano! El océano necesita nuestra ayuda, y hay muchas actividades divertidas que puedes hacer para restaurarlo. ¡Vamos a descubrir qué acciones ya estás tomando y cuáles te gustaría probar para ayudar a que nuestros océanos sean más saludables!

*** ¿Cuánto sabes sobre cómo ayudar al océano? (Elige una)**

- ¡Sé mucho! Ya he ayudado al océano antes.
- Sé algunas cosas, y quiero hacer más.
- Aún no sé mucho, pero me gustaría aprender.

*** ¿Cuáles de estas actividades has hecho para ayudar a restaurar el océano? (Elige todas las que apliquen)**

- Participé en acciones de restauración.
- Ayudé a proteger animales como tortugas, peces o aves marinas.
- Ayudé a limpiar playas o ríos para que sean más saludables para la vida marina.
- Aprendí o enseñé a otros cómo restaurar el océano.
- Aún no he hecho ninguna de estas actividades, ¡pero estoy listo para empezar!

*** ¿Qué actividad de restauración del océano te gustaría probar? (Elige hasta 3)**

- Ser voluntario para ayudar a cultivar arrecifes de coral.
- Ayudar a plantar o proteger praderas marinas.
- Unirme u organizar un evento de restauración de playas o ríos.
- Aprender a proteger animales oceánicos en peligro.
- Crear carteles o videos para enseñar a otros sobre cómo salvar el océano.
- Aprender cómo los científicos restauran áreas dañadas del océano.

*** ¿Cómo crees que podrías ayudar a proteger a los animales en el océano? (Elige una)**

- Ayudar a restaurar sus hábitats plantando arrecifes de coral.
- Aprender más sobre lo que necesitan para estar seguros y saludables.
- Animar a otros a proteger las áreas oceánicas donde viven los animales.
- Apoyar proyectos que ayuden a la recuperación de animales marinos.

*** ¿Qué podrías hacer hoy para que el océano sea más saludable? (Elige una)**

- Hablar con mis amigos o familia sobre el océano.
- Unirme a un evento local de restauración de playas o ríos.
- Aprender más sobre los arrecifes de coral y cómo ayudan al océano.
- Averiguar cómo puedo ayudar a científicos o proyectos que restauran el océano.

*** ¿Qué pequeño cambio podrías comenzar a hacer hoy para ayudar a proteger el océano? (Elige una)**

- Usaré una botella de agua reutilizable.
- Recogeré basura cuando la vea cerca del océano o ríos.
- Buscaré una iniciativa local de restauración del océano para unirme.
- Aprenderé más sobre los animales del océano y cómo ayudarlos.
- Usaré menos agua en casa.

Si pudieras hacer otra cualquier cosa para ayudar al océano, ¿qué sería?

Contact

ivansavieira@spi.pt

1

Pesca de Arrastre

Este tipo de pesca utiliza redes gigantes que arrastran el fondo marino, destruyendo hábitats frágiles y especies.

2

Sabías que...

Los arrecifes de coral albergan más del 25% de la vida marina, a pesar de cubrir menos del 1% del fondo oceánico

3

Replantación de Pastos Marinos

Recolectar semillas de pastos marinos y replantarlas en áreas degradadas ayuda a estabilizar los sedimentos y mejora la biodiversidad.

1

Contaminación por Plásticos

Los plásticos y microplásticos vertidos en el océano pueden sofocar los ecosistemas marinos y afectar a los organismos del fondo.

2

Sabías que...

Los pastos marinos pueden capturar carbono hasta 35 veces más rápido que los bosques terrestres.

3

Restauración de Arrecifes de Coral

Trasplantar corales cultivados en viveros a arrecifes dañados para regenerar áreas afectadas por el blanqueamiento o la pesca destructiva.

1

Sobrepescatre

La extracción masiva de peces interrumpe el equilibrio del ecosistema y puede llevar al colapso de especies clave.

2

Sabías que...

Cada año, se vierten aproximadamente 8 millones de toneladas de plástico en los océanos. Estos plásticos pueden tardar cientos de años en descomponerse.

3

Creación de Áreas Marinas Protegidas

Establecer áreas protegidas para evitar la pesca de arrastre y otras actividades destructivas.

1

Destrucción de Arrecifes de Coral

Actividades humanas como la pesca con dinamita o el turismo irresponsable pueden dañar los corales.

2

Sabías que...

Los arrecifes artificiales no solo ayudan a las especies marinas, sino que también protegen las costas de la erosión y actúan como barreras naturales.

3

Siembra de Larvas de Ostras

Las ostras juveniles se colocan en lechos restaurados para repoblar y formar nuevos arrecifes de ostras.

1

Turismo Irresponsable en Arrecifes

Buceadores y turistas tocan y dañan los corales o tiran basura en zonas protegidas.

2

Sabías que...

Las ostras adultas pueden filtrar hasta 190 litros de agua por día, lo que ayuda a mantener la claridad y calidad del agua.

3

Cultivo de Corales en Viveros

Los corales jóvenes son cultivados en viveros bajo condiciones controladas antes de ser trasplantados a arrecifes en recuperación.

1

Vertidos de Petróleo

Los derrames de petróleo en el mar pueden destruir hábitats enteros al cubrir el fondo marino y sofocar la vida acuática marina, destruyendo hábitats frágiles y especies.

2

Sabías que...

Las boyas de amarre protegen los corales del daño causado por las anclas de barcos que los destruyen al anclarse cerca de arrecifes.

3

Uso de Boyas de Amarre

En lugar de anclar barcos directamente en el fondo marino, se utilizan boyas de amarre en áreas protegidas.

1

Acidificación de los Océanos

El exceso de dióxido de carbono en la atmósfera es absorbido por los océanos, bajando el pH del agua y dañando ecosistemas como los arrecifes de corales.

2

Sabías que...

Los bosques de algas marinas pueden crecer hasta medio metro al día y ofrecen refugio a miles de especies marinas. Sin embargo, el aumento de la población de erizos de mar puede arrasar con estos bosques.

3

Limpieza de Fondos Marinos

Grupos de voluntarios bucean para retirar plásticos, redes fantasmas y otros residuos del fondo del océano

1

Pesca Ilegal con Explosivos

El uso de dinamita para capturar peces destruye el hábitat del fondo marino y mata indiscriminadamente a toda la vida marina en el área.

2

Sabías que...

Más del 50% de los corales del mundo están en peligro por el cambio climático y la contaminación.

3

Creación de Arrecifes Artificiales

Se construyen arrecifes artificiales con roca caliza o restos de naufragios antiguos, promoviendo la formación de nuevos hábitats.

2

Sabías que...

Los pastos marinos ayudan a absorber el carbono, lo que los convierte en aliados en la lucha contra el cambio climático.

2

2

Sabías que...

Los arrecifes de coral actúan como barreras naturales, protegiendo las costas de las olas y las tormentas.

2

4

Preguntas

¿Qué actividad destructiva puede dañar los arrecifes de coral?

4

Preguntas

¿Qué mala práctica podría destruir rápidamente estos importantes ecosistemas?

4

Preguntas

¿Qué buena práctica ayuda a restaurar y mantener los corales y pastos marinos, importantes captadores de carbono?

4

Preguntas

¿Qué mala práctica está destruyendo hábitats en las profundidades oceánicas?

4

Preguntas

¿Qué buena práctica fomenta la creación de nuevos hábitats marinos y protege las costas?

4

Preguntas

¿Qué buena práctica apoya la regeneración de los lechos de ostras?

4

Preguntas

¿Qué mala práctica podría ser evitada con la instalación de boyas de amarre?

4

Preguntas

¿Qué mala práctica está destruyendo hábitats en las profundidades oceánicas?

4

Preguntas

¿Qué práctica humana contribuye a la destrucción de los arrecifes de coral?

4

Preguntas

¿Cómo se puede restaurar los pastos marinos degradados?

2024